

INDIAN CONSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR IDENTITY POLITICS AND IDENTITY MOVEMENTS

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Abstract

Developing some sort of identity is an obligatory outcome because every civilization is, in one way or another, a product of a location, way of life, gender, race, polity, or any other social construct. Here, the idea of society is broadened to include all social phenomena and is identified by collective characteristics. Thus, India's tremendous splits and partitions have contributed to the rise in identity politics. Pluralism and Multiculturalism have evolved into identity politics, with definite groups being defined by their race or ethnicity, leading to a desire for political dominance. The process of developing social identities based on a variety of factors, such as religion and race, is known as identity development. Identity can cause differences between diverse groups in a number of ways. For example, caste, language, and even religion are not minor elements in Indian politics today; rather, they are major determinants of regional politics. In addition, in Indian states where liberal politics predominate, this kind of issue-focused attention leads to a significant imbalance in the development processes. The laws of several multi-national states, where cultural preservation is prioritized, codify the national, ethnic, or religious rights of these minority of the "others" is especially incidental. Social, political, and economic repercussions result from these considerations of nations and cultural diversity.

Keywords: *Identity, Collective Actions, Democratisation Social Movements, Recognition,*

Introduction:

There have been several movements throughout the world's civilization history that have significantly altered the existing social structures. Numerous movements have also failed in

the end. The beliefs of these movements have significantly differed; some advocate major revisions to conservatism, while others have a more wide scope. For example, some have a worldwide scope, while others are only local. Experts have conducted extensive research to understand the origins of these activities, the individuals whose interests are included into them, and those who do not, despite the fact that they differ in many ways. Participate in them, the causes of their achievements, and above all their failures. The word was initially used in a European language in the early 1800s, according to the history of social movements (Shah, 2002). The goal of collective action was always to change the status quo, according to the early historians. Analyzing the broad phenomenon of collective achievement and figuring out what would be needed to promote social movement was one of the first works on social movements. The life cycle of social movements was outlined in four succeeding stages by Herbert Blumer, a Latino-Jewish specialist on the subject. According to Diani & De La Porta (2006), he distinguished four stages: "social foment," "popular excitement," "formalization," and "institutionalization."

It can be difficult to define what a social movement is. It is not an interest group or political party, which are both dependable political organizations with consistent access to political elites and power. Additionally, it is not merely a fleeting craze or trend, which frequently lacks structure and specific objectives. Rather, a middle ground is occupied by social movements (Freeman and Johnson, 1999). Social movements are characterized by their involvement in "conflictual connections with clearly defined opponents; related by (De La Porta and Diani, 2006) "and they share a distinct collective identity; dense informal networks." Consequently, an organized but unofficial social entity involved in extra-constitutional dispute that is focused on certain goals or objectives—which may be limited or widely aiming at comprehensive change—can be regarded as a social movement. Paul Wilkinson asserts that two essential components are essential for a significant degree of organization and dedication to change is characteristics of a social movement (Shah, 2002).

When socioeconomic circumstances cause discontent with the existing system, social movements are born. People join these groups for a variety of reasons, such as political goals, idealism, compassion, and even frustrated neurotic. The beginnings of social movements are mainly explained by three opposing theories: the theory of revitalization, the theory of strain, and the theory of relative deprivation. Stauffer coined the term "Relative Deprivation" in 1949. It implies that people suffer a sense of deprivation as a result of the gap between their expectations and reality. A person, who has little and wants little, for example, will feel less

deprived than someone who has a lot but expects still more. Relative deprivation theorists emphasize that social activity is not always the result of merely existing in a state of relative deprivation. Relative deprivation's structural circumstances are crucial. According to Rao (1978), adequate conditions result from people's perceptions of their circumstances and leaders' conviction that they can act to make things better. According to Neil Smelser's 1962 Strain Theory, structural stresses are the primary forces influencing group behavior. Social mobility, norms, and values are just a few of the levels at which these stresses may appear. Smelser's analysis of the beginnings of social movements is consistent with a structural functional framework, which sees stress as a danger to a system's linkages that could cause it to malfunction. Feelings of deprivation are also highlighted by this hypothesis. According to the theories of strain and relative deprivation, social movements usually start as a result of adverse situations like strain and deprivation. Conversely, Wallace, who promoted the Cultural Revitalization thesis, contends that social movements are the result of society's members making a deliberate and coordinated attempt to build a more satisfying culture. According to this viewpoint, adaptive processes are employed to attain equilibrium. These movements have two sides to them; in addition to expressing discontent and protesting against the status quo, additionally suggest positive measures to deal with the current problems, as Rao pointed out in 1978.

A more recent development in social movements, identity movements come in a variety of forms. Collective acts are the main component of these movements, which are intended to promote the rights and interests of particular excluded groups and to win others' symbolic acknowledgment. This essay will examine the idea of identity, describe the traits of identity movements, and talk about how they have affected Indian states.

Movements of Identity:

The twentieth-century identity movements are very different from one another because they reflect two complimentary forms of group demands: (a) the protection of the rights of those who feel discriminated against, and (b) the desire for symbolic approval from a significant person. These movements have three primary goals, each of which is quite unique. First, they draw attention to the inequalities that minorities. Second, they stress how crucial it is to take particular cultures into account when creating public policies that cater to the particular requirements of these groups. Third, some of them support self-government, while others want more authority over their institutions (Smelser, 2001). In his edited book "Social Movements I – Issues of Identity," T. K. Oommen makes the case that none of the founding

fathers—Durkheim, Marx and Weber provided succinct and straightforward explanations of social movements or group activities. A perceptive observer can see, nevertheless, that their early justifications of group behavior are intricately entwined with their social assessments. These days, academics in the humanities and social sciences describe their work as fundamental to the philosophy of collective action. The European society Emile Durkheim lived in was characterized by a collapsing social life, unhappy people, and a great deal of conflict. The idea of collective action is based on his fundamental ideas of communal consciousness and collective representation; without the former, collective action cannot start, and without the latter, the changes that take place cannot be conveyed clearly. In his 1883 article "The Division of Labor in Society," Durkheim first presented a theory of collective action and social transformation. He later studied the kinds of solidarity that support, ritualize, and justify forms of collective action in "Elementary Forms of Religious Life" (1915). He paints a picture of a society torn between integrating and dissolving forces (rapid differentiation).

Politics in India and Identity Movements:

During the 1947–1948 period following independence, India was split into Pakistan and India on the basis of religion. Following independence, the nation had to deal with the crucial issue of defining the borders of Indian states, which are split along religious, caste, and ethnic lines. Linguistic, cultural, and regional basis. Maintaining the unity and integrity of a nation split into multiple ethno-cultural and linguistic groupings was the principal responsibility of the just established government. In the post-independence era, 782 mother tongues were registered in the first census in 1951, and that number rose to 1,652 in 1961. In 1971, it dropped to 1,019, and in 1991, it rose once more to 1,576 (Oommen, nd. www.sciencedirect.com). Reducing and containing ethno-cultural disputes and issues was the main goal of the newly independent India in such a culturally and linguistically diverse population. At the time, a nation's main goal was to encourage swift and equitable economic growth while maintaining equity and fairness. The growth and development of various regions were barely balanced, despite the Indian government's best efforts. This caused a sense of deprivation among the various communities or groups, which subsequently manifested itself in movements and protests. India is currently experiencing severe unrest and upheavals sixty-six years after gaining its independence. It has experienced intercommunal riots and a strengthening of religious bonds among certain minority; for example, it has seen caste- and class-based campaigns for reservation and protection, in addition to other

movements like workers' movements, such as the peasant and farmer movements, have defined the current Indian states. The major secessionist movement in a portion of the nation has been the most significant of all. The recognition of their unique ethnic identities is a commonality shared by the majority, if not all, of the movements in these states, despite the fact that their objectives, ideologies, and methods paint a complicated and varied picture. Usually, the goal of these movements is to demand collective rights. And benefits for the defense and acknowledgment of a group or community on the basis of their unique identity (race, caste, culture, language, area, etc.), occasionally by establishing a separate state inside the Indian Union.

After independence, India faces a significant challenge in maintaining unity and integrity due to its diverse ethnic and cultural groupings. One of the consequences of this variety is the emerging sociopolitical movement in many parts of the country. The presence of such groups has had a significant impact on Indian politics, including the constitution and the formation of regional political parties. India's development strategy after independence tried to address ethnic issues and conflicts. According to Currie (1996), the model is based on a mixed economic framework that includes both private capital and a state-owned public sector. The model aimed to foster equitable and balanced economic growth (Dandekar, 1988). The Indian center's dedication to social welfare played a vital influence in the socio-economic growth of ethnic communities, enabling direct regulation of politics and the economy in India. In practice, however, the growth of various ethnic groupings the uneven distribution of resources across the country led to perceptions of deprivation among towns and provinces.

In the 1950s, the Indian state underwent administrative reorganization to support regional and ethno-cultural identities. The State Reorganization Commission was founded in 1953, and the State Reorganization Act was passed in 1956. The Act created fourteen. There are new states and five Union Territories. The establishment of new nations in 1956 did not resolve ethnic and cultural disputes. Instead, different statehood movements emerged based on ethnic, regional, and linguistic grounds. The Indian state posed a challenge to democracy. The Bombay Reorganization Act of 1960 established Maharashtra and Gujarat based on language. Nagaland was formed by separating Assam in 1962. In 1966, Haryana was formed by separating Punjab. In the North East region, three states were established: Meghalaya Manipur and Tripura were established in 1971. However, the need for new states based on ethnic identity was not limited. Some regions of the country continue to advocate for their own state based on their unique identity.

Reservation politics in Indian states is driven by identity politics, attracting attention from political leaders and academics alike. The Preamble of the Constitution outlines a commitment to social, economic, and political fairness. Quotas and reservations have been implemented in different sectors, including education, government employment, and legislative representation, to encourage inclusivity. The Indian constitution recognizes two groups: schedule castes and schedule tribes, who have historically been denied certain rights and advantages. Since independence, India has reserved seats in parliament for historically underprivileged communities. Schedule both caste and tribe. The notion of 'positive discrimination' has sparked debate in India regarding reservations for historically marginalized groups. However, it has also highlighted the concept of OBC (other backward communities). Positive discrimination policies have led to political problems within states, as more groups demand to be included in these categories.

Conclusion

Despite Indian authorities' efforts to develop fair institutions and processes for addressing identity aspirations and demands, ethnic disputes continue to arise. The Indian state's administrative reorganization in the 1950s emphasized ethno-linguistic and regional identities, responding to calls for new states formed based on broad ethno linguistic parameters. The British ignored pre-independence demands due to concerns about fueling ethno-nationalist sentiments. Residents of the Darjeeling hills have long advocated for an independent state of Gorkhaland outside West Bengal. Similarly, the Kamtapur movement by the Rajbanshi people in Cooch Behar, as well as the Bodoland movement in Assam and the Telangana movement, have a long history. Challenges to India's unity include Andhra Pradesh, Vidarbha in Maharashtra, and a demand for a separate Jammu and Kashmir state.

These movements have successfully lobbied for change and influenced Indian state politics at the regional and national levels, in addition to their insurgent actions. Nonetheless, these movements have not they have had a significant impact on Indian pluralism and should be taken seriously. The Indian constitution's provisions, such as the Fifth and Sixth Schedules for special administrative structures at district levels and Article 370 for Jammu and Kashmir, effectively counter the claims of such groups. Articles 371A, 371F, and 371G of the Kashmir constitution grant unique advantages to Nagaland, Sikkim, and Mizoram, which are North East states. In addition, the Indian constitution allows for the formation of new states based on diverse group identities within the union. In addition to their insurgent actions, these movements are well-known for their successful lobbying campaigns, which have a big impact

on regional and national politics in Indian states and propel change. Although Indian pluralism has not been significantly impacted by these movements, they undoubtedly have an impact that cannot be disregarded. The Indian constitution's provisions have made a significant attempt to meet these parties' issues. For example, the constitution's Fifth and Sixth Schedules create unique district-level administrative frameworks, while Article With its own constitution, 370 offers Jammu and Kashmir a special arrangement. Furthermore, the northeastern states of Nagaland, Sikkim, and Mizoram are granted exceptional privileges under Articles 371A, 371F, and 371G. In addition, the constitution provides for the establishment of new states inside the Indian union that are based on various group identities.

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